

THE REALITY AND IRONY OF HUMANISM

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Introduction

Among everything that exists, man is central, but also the weakest and consequently, appears most care-deserving and pathetic. To be humane but not humbug therefore, is supposedly man's nature. Also, he is seen as the most intelligible being that creates, explains and defines himself and his environment in a coherent rationality. Following this, the dignity of man must be restored through humanism and its revitalization. Thus, the question of humanism is philosophically central, for it holistically deepens into human existence and affairs. As the acclaimed most intelligible being, the outcome of his attitude supposedly ought to portray his intelligibility and humanism, but ironical enough, this is rarely the case. He claims to have solved his social problems with his human intelligence only to end up creating more problems for himself through his intellectual conceptions, theories and practices. The question is: has man truly by his intellectuality resolved his existential challenges?

Key word: Reality, irony and humanism

The Concept of Humanism

The term “humanism” is derived from the root word– “human” which connotes the idea of *human beings* instead of “animals”, plants or vegetations and other inanimate and even God or gods. Thus, human beings are *conceptually* placed more rationally and morally valued, than other physical beings. Humanism as a concept is vague, but we will limit it to two conceptions in order to remain within a given scope. In the *first sense*, it implies “a system of thought that considers that solving human problems with the help of reason is more important than religious beliefs”. Humanism here portrays man as a rational being who is conceived to be intelligible enough to use his rationality, intelligibility to solve his social problems rather than depending on religious solutions which may sometimes be characteristically biased and subjective. In the *second sense*, it depicts the fact that “the basic nature of humans is good”. Here portrays the fundamental “theo-nature” of man as a product of the “Good”, *Imago Dei* (Image of God) and as such, should be humane to himself, his neighbours and general environment. These two conceptions are in agreement with each other for the first presupposes the second. That is, with our human rationality, we should be able to come up

with rational and humane ideas as guides and directives in our daily functions and for our better livelihood. Human beings prove their intelligibility on daily basis through researches and their findings (theories), some equally try to be humane as they can even though among natural factors are ignorance and inhumanity. However, the irony (problem) is that the products of their humanism (theories) which are proofs of their intelligibility, encourage inhumanity. Most calamities that have befallen man are encouraged by some of his intellectual outputs or ideas.

To this end, some theorists or intellectuals hold that rationality is the primacy of all beings, and by implication, the ignorant is doomed; or perhaps, the level of your rationality determines the level of humane attitude that will be meted out for you. This prompted some great minds to justify the predicaments (slavery, colonization, neo-colonization, racism, etc) that befell the Africans. In fact for Kant, the poor rationality of the Africans is purely epitomized in their blackness hence he says, “this fellow was quite black from head to foot; a clear proof that what he says was stupid” (Sertqueberham, 1991:6.) The blackness of the African, which some Africans (Senghor, 1965:45-6, Cesaire, 1972:72, Damas, 1969:545) conceived as the African personality and distinctive pride which

should be held high and be proud of, is a proof of the African illogicality, senselessness, stupidity and irrationality. Speaking on this, Okolo (1996:iii) has earlier said that “‘to be black’ was in reality equated with being poor, illiterate, inferior, subservient, an object of exploitation, etc” while “‘to be white’ was officially the exact opposite, namely, to be rich, educated, superior, masterful and so on.” Be that as it may, the point remains that for some thinkers, Africans deserved those predicaments because they are not rational and their colour depicts that. In Hegel’s word: “What we properly understand by Africa, is the Unhistorical, Undeveloped Spirit, still involved in the conditions of mere nature, and which had to be present only as on the threshold of the world’s history” (1956:99.) In other words, “in Negro life, the characteristic point is that consciousness has not yet attained the realization of any substantial objective existence in which the interest of man’s volition is involved and in which he realizes his own being” (93.) Some justified these inhumanities because by comparison, they thought, the Africans are very poor when compared to their European counterparts. Williams has this to say:

Compared with the white races, he seems to lack initiative and constructive ideas, although he may be shrewd judge of the attainment of others... Power of observation is astonishingly defective... They seem to be incapable of sustained effort... An African has little imagination... His self-esteem is often ludicrous... The qualities most in need of education are imagination and judgment (Carothers, 1972:95)

Going further, some hold that reality is entirely physical, and therefore, the ideals (invisibles) are non-existents. The implication here is the negligence of the invisible (essence or substance) which is a very dangerous type of life because the value and dignity of life are in question. On the other hand, some hold that reality is entirely ideal (invisible) and so, the physical is only illusion. The implication here is the possibility of inhuman attitudes towards the physical when idealism extremely leads us to the domain of nothingness. Some hold that reality is an encompassment of physical and non-physical. But whereas some argue that primacy should be attributed to the physical, some holds the very opposite. Nevertheless, the problem here is our inability to detect their contact-point and the justified effects of the supremacy of one on the other.

This said however, the supposedly necessity of humanism in ensuring the welfare of man is clear and indubitable but the unfortunate fact is that the products of human rationality today have become the central problems of man and have raised some philosophical questions. What is supposed to be the way to safety has become the way to disaster all in the name of proving the best (of intellectuality) in us. We claim we now know things and things in turn know us. We have intellectually articulated certain ideas and issues that we now intelligibly argue as our rights for some acts that are anti-nature like homosexuality, lesbianism, and defense of actions that contradict human sense of reason, etc. Some of these are self-imposed troubles from the exercise of our intellectuality. But it seems that man has forgotten that the ignorance of Nature is more reasonable than his wisdom. Man today challenges Nature in different angles making truly some commendable impacts but indirectly creating more worries to his existence. He seems to forget the essence of the saying that *amaghi m ka nwata jiri muru okwu* (I do not know is the first word of a child) which shows the natural ignorance of man no matter how intelligible he may claim. In ignorance and child-like man begins, and in ignorance and child-like too man ends his existential journey. Truly, there are some intellectual outcomes (theories, systems, ways of life and philosophies) that are ideally and practically positive in the society, but some are otherwise, war-motivating, inhumane and nasty, morally-inconsiderate and eventually misleading. At this juncture, let us selectively, critically and carefully discuss some theories cum doctrines to portray our cause of discourse here.

Existentialism: This is a philosophical movement that stresses that existence precedes whatever a thing becomes (essence) in life. It emphasizes the facticity of “firstness” of existence (life in this sense) before any other life-ingredient for it is when a thing exists as a being, that it will give meaning, vitality or essence to itself. But even as existentialism holds life at the highest esteem, it still accommodates the irony (absurdity and meaninglessness) of life. This informs Sartre’s position that “it is absurd that we are born, it is absurd that we die.” Death he thought shows the irony of life for “if we have to die, then, our life has no meaning” (1969:545.) Seeing life as a misery, Job even asks why men should be left in misery all in the name of living. Life is a contradiction itself and has been the most incomprehensible of all phenomena. “What a chimera is man, a bundle of

contradiction!” To conclude this, Pascal (1966:237-52) exclaims:

Man is nothing but a subject full of natural error that cannot be eradicated except through grace.

Nothing shows him the truth, everything deceives him. The two principles of truth, reason and senses, are not only both not genuine, but are engaged in natural deception. The sense deceives reason through false appearances, and just as they trick the soul, they are tricked by it in their turn: it takes its revenge. The senses are disturbed by passions which produce false impression. They both compete in lies and deception

Personalism: This is a theory that emphasizes the fundamentality or primacy of the individual person whose indubitable existential presuppositions—dignity, integrity, human respect, right and freedom must be restored as the first step to meaningful existence and discourse on human beings. It “emphasizes the inviolable dignity of every man by the very fact of being a human being” which must be recognized as the first principle of general existence. According to Omoregbe (2011:196):

Personalism protests against the tendencies in modern societies to depreciate the absolute value of the human person. It protests against all the de-personalizing forces in modern societies and maintains that man is the key to the understanding of the whole reality. The human person transcends the infra-human world. (It) rejects the view that man is completely part of nature, for man... transcends nature. The human person possesses an inviolable dignity, an inalienable liberty, and an inescapable moral responsibility. It is an offence against human dignity to treat the human person as an object. Hence, personalism decries the exploitation, instrumentalisation and de-personalization of human persons

From here, it is clear that personalism projects the philosophy of *man, know yourself and worth or value*. It is on “personalism” that Heidegger stands and makes his philosophical development, and also criticizes the Western Metaphysics on the question of being. He opines that instead of recognizing the

being who asks fundamental questions about his existence and environment, the Western Ontology rather recognizes the activity of the being as the fundamental reality just as Descartes did. He accuses the Western thinkers of burying the knowledge of being and counting “two” before “one”; that is, attributing primacy to the activity of *Dasein* (man) instead of *Dasein* himself and the consequence is establishing a parlance of knowledge characterized by *nothingness and abstractness* just like Kant did in his metaphysics, and the implication is nothing but inhumanity (Heidegger, 1973:289-311.) Personalism does not agree with Russell’s position that “man is part of nature, not something contracted with nature. His thoughts and... bodily movements follow the same laws that describe the motions of the stars and atoms” (1967:43.)

Idealism, Essentialism and Vitalism: These theories and doctrines underscore the followings: the primacy of the ideal in contradistinction to what is the real, (Runes, 1995:354) the existence of essence and its primacy and superiority to the physical components of beings, and that “life cannot be explained by physical, chemical and mechanical laws of growth... reproduction” or any other physical, scientific or biological means but by the concept of *entelechy* which is a soul or mind-like and non-spatial element “which controls the course of organic process” and even survives death. The fact remains that primacy is attributed to the abstract-life-phenomenon hence the care of the abstract is principal than the care of the physical (Eneh, 2001:146) and uniting and fulfilling the tenets of the ideal preoccupies every being. The danger in this theory is that when the knowledge and primacy of the ideal, essence and vital element is not tamed, it can lead to abstract parlance (nothingness) where there is no life let alone being humane to fellow men hence everything has been spiritualized.

Stoicism: This is a theory that emphasizes the principle of being unmoved or indifference to avoid the fallacy of *argumentum ad misericordiam* (judgments from sentiments or emotional influences). It holds that man should be free from passions or being moved by joy or pain. It upholds a universal consideration or brotherhood where no “special” consideration is given to some people or group instead of all who are involved.

Humanism: This is the philosophic way of living where the preservation and value of human life is prior and must be restored through the concept of

community-living where each is inseparably dutiful to the other. It is a philosophy of *be your brother's keeper* guided by the principle of existentialism, personalism, vitalism and stoicism. It emphasizes “social consciousness and kindness to other people. Selfishness and individualism are vices... traditionally the African is (*sic*) his brother's keeper concerned about the welfare of his neighbor and that of community in which he lives” (Omoregbe, 199.)

Realism: This is a theory that is mild in treating the issues of both the spiritual and the physical. It holds that the both exist but not in different existential spheres as Plato tells us. Man is thus a bundle of the *ideal* and the *physical* in a real presence but primacy is given to the *form*. Though an alteration in the *form* presupposes such in the *matter* and as a result, causes substantial alteration.

Utilitarianism: This is a doctrine that claims that the action that favours greater number of the people should be upheld. So, the morality and encouragement of an action is based on the number of people who benefit from it; but what is the yardstick for measuring a value? Or what is the place of reason if the action contradicts natural reason, but based on socio-political cum cultural influence, it favours many and seen as moral? Be that as may, altruism and liberality are still central in utilitarianism.

Naturalism, Atomism and Materialism: These are philosophical theories that proclaim that reality is found in nature- in this physical world as it is found, that primary reality behind everything existing—whether abstract or physical— is atom, that the fundamentality of every reality is nothing spiritual but primarily material. The clear problem arising from them is that human dignity is in danger for they can inculcate in people hedonism, survival of the fittest and misconception of life and its value, and enhance universal inhumanity hence the physical is all that matters. The influence is clear in the Hobbesian Leviathan, Ryle's and La Mettrie's conceptualization of man and his spirituality as the “Ghost in Machine”, Holbach's “Unfreely Rolling Big Stone” from the hill down to the valley, etc.

Sophism: This is a view that stresses the power of logic, linguistic construction and grammatical influence in approaching life-issues. It argues for the subjectivity or relativity of value, uncertainty of knowledge and the claim that justice and right are power and might. In as much as you can be logically affective and linguistically plausible, influential and bold enough to argue that the United States of

America is now Nigeria or say that Abraham Lincoln is today's Nigerian president, and gain supporters, then that is the truth. As a theory, it makes subjectivism, lies and fallacies, its functional tools and as such, is one of the dangerous theories.

Individualism: This theory holds that the oneness or singularity of ideas/beings is the *oughtness* and reality of existence. It does not allow for the collectivity or communality of life. It is in direct opposition to the core philosophical tenet in communalism, and as a result, people should socially be individualized. The problem of the relativity of value is prominent here as it brings about a life of dividedness and serves as the principle of incoherence and disunity in life.

At this juncture, the clear fact is the possibility of both negative and positive influences of human thoughts and their articulations. Articulated ideas have been forces, objects or instincts of motivation behind many movements and global occurrences. Ideas articulated by some thinkers incite in people the mentality of superiority over others and seeing others as sub-humans upon which they think that any inhuman attitude to these ‘sub-humans’ are morally justified. Ideas truly rule the world and greatly determine history. To this end, the world came up with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the 1789 Right Declaration by France and the 1776 Independence Declaration by the United States of America, at the end of the 2nd World War to avert such inhumanity on humanity having seen the grave effects. But both the 1st and 2nd World Wars were products of race-base, war-motivated, radical and inhuman articulated ideologies. Be that as may, let us now point out some theorists and the possible effects from their thoughts.

Heraclitus: This Asian-Minor Ephesian posits that the reality behind everything that is, is nothing but change characteristically expressed in the traits of fire. For him, change which portrays the principle of opposite is the underlying principle in the universe through which progress emerges and existence explained. By this, he encouraged war, and glorifying war as the principle of progress, he opined that “war is both king of all father of all and it has revealed some as gods, others as men; some it has made slaves, others free” (Drew, 1973.)

Empedocles: This Sicilian holds that the primordial stuffs with which everything is made include: earth, water, air and fire. He recognizes two principles—of unification (love or harmony) and separation (hate, opposition, disagreement or disorder) in explaining reality. For him just like Heraclitus and the Atomists, these principles of opposition explain and ensure the progress and continuity of reality and ought to be sought for.

Machiavelli: This Italian political thinker and prophet of force holds that “the preoccupation of a ruler even at the time of peace, must be on how to acquire the skill in war and its organization.” This presupposes that “the art of war is all that is expected of a ruler and it is so useful that besides enabling hereditary princes to maintain their rule, it frequently enables ordinary citizens to become rulers.” He, just like Hobbes, propagated the idea that a ruler ought to go to any length provided he controls his government. Their thoughts originated absolutism in human affairs. He encouraged the brutality of the courageous, fearless, powerful and absolute dictatorial ruler by positing that he “must be a fox in order to recognize traps and lion to frighten off wolves” so that he will “colour his actions and to be a great liar and deceiver.” A good ruler thus must ignore compassion but take up brutality and sword and cruelty to keep the subjects and his army in unity, loyalty and under fear. His thought and that of Florentine thinker and Dominican friar- Girolamo Savonarola espoused the historical brutality, deceptive rulership, ruthlessness and viciousness in Italy and indeed the whole world.

Neitzsche: This German existentialist preaches that existence is the principal before essence and that to exist is to be free. He holds that it is in this existence that man, in his full freedom, will realize himself and conquer “collectivity” of any sort. In the bid to develop his existential fundamental concept (freedom), he writes that “man shall be educated for war and women for procreation of the warriors; everything else is folly”. He is of uncompassionate and inhumane, and in that, advising that “compassion for all would amount to tyranny for you, my dear neighbour.” Even in our theories that stress humanism, we end up inhuman.

Martin Buber: This Jewish-German projected humanism in his *I-Thou and I-It Relationship* and opines “that no one who counts himself in the ranks of Israel can desire to use force.” Ironically at the same time, he ended up preaching ‘war against war’ and upheld Iraq for resisting the “American Force”

and encouraged the Jews to resist the German inhumanity to them. In his “Doctrine of the Sword”, he advised his people to reject the Gandhian Non-Violence for they were going into existential extinction and oblivion, hence he said that “strength does not come from physical capacity, it comes from an indomitable will”.

Hitler: This former German Chancellor and “Third Reich Fuhrer” (leader) believed so much in his assumed superiority of the German race over any other race on earth, and so, the Germans should be recognized as best specie of human beings. In his bid to actualize that, he enhanced the 2nd World War which primarily aimed at total annihilation of the ever-progressing-Jews. He thus opined that progressive and successful rulership is the one that lies in the “might of a triumphant sword”. He “used state terrorism, violence, suppression and intrigues to achieve his desire for glory,” power-attainment and keeping steady the Third Reich from 1933-45. In practical inhumanism, Hitler administered a certain poison to Eva Braun- his wife before he finally committed the shooting suicide in 1945 to end Nazism but before this, appealed to his body-guard to burn his corpse when he goes and that body-guard fulfilled it for him- Hitler.

From these analyses, we can see that some thinkers used their ideas to enhance series of tyrannical and brutal rulership globally experienced. The inhumanity and disregard by some powerful emperors like Claudius Caesar Nero, Vespasian, Domitian, Trajan, Antonius, Marcus Aurelius, the African Septimus Severus and famous Constantine in his “Roman-Empire-Christianization”, among others who sworn for the eradication of Christianity were ideally motivated by some articulated theories (outcomes of humanism and intellectuality). Kaplan (23) recorded the inhumanity of Constantine for instance saying:

Constantine and his clergymen at the Council of Nicea quickly began enacting a series of restrictive Edicts against the Jewish people. His purpose was to separate the Gentiles and Jews from worshipping together. In his words, he considered the Jews an “evil and perverse sect... let us have nothing to do with the Jews who are our adversaries, in order that we no more have anything in common with these parasites and murderers of our Lord”

The 2nd World War Italian Prime Minister, Benito Mussolini was a professed dictator who would incarcerate, oppress and finally murder his citizens in the prison. Joseph Stalin- Lois Vissarinovich Dzhugashili was an ex-seminarian but whom after the Russian Revolution in the 1950s, resorted to dictatorship, and murdered his citizens and even some of the Revolutionists like Leo Trotsky and their wives like Mrs. Kalinin and Motolov, among others. Pehlavi- the Iran Shah, with the use of his Secret Police (Savak) dehumanized his opponent citizens till when the people got provoked and forced him out of office in 1979. All these are the outcomes of the ideas of Great Minds like Heraclitus, the Atomists who believed in progress through war and Hitler, Machiavelli, Hobbes who did not only believe in war but also encouraged extremism characterized by brutality provided power is retained and ‘forceful’ peace is maintained. Even in Africa, the influence from some theories motivating inhumanism and brutality was also experienced. It was the brain behind the autocratic rulership, tyranny, inhumanity and brutality of people like Idi Amin of Uganda, Jean Bedel Bokassa of the Central African Republic, Mobutu Seso Seko of Zaire who never even spoke Zairean language, Haile Selassie- nicknamed “Lion of Judah” of Ethiopia, Kamuzu Banda of Malawi, Gaddafi of Libya, among others (Eneh, 2011:93-103.) Apart from being natural, and even when it is natural, such inhumane theories enkindled actions of such.

The irony of humanism even from the “church”

Even in the face of religion where man thinks that the revival and safety of mankind is guaranteed, man keeps experiencing negativity of humanism (egoism, deception and human-degradation and discriminatory ideologies). Supposedly, religion ought to play vital roles in reinstating humanism and ensuring human welfare. Giving his submission, Abbot (1976) has this to say:

From the various religions, men accept answers to the secret enigmas of the human conditions

which deeply-troubled the human heart yesterday as they do today. Man’s nature, the meaning and end of our life, good and sin, the origin and aim of suffering, the way to reach true happiness, death, judgment and sanction after death, finally, the ultimate and ineffable

mystery which envelops our existence where we came from and where we are going

Unfortunately, this supposed role of religion is no more as the church has irreparably derailed and the opposite has become our daily experience afterwards. In his *Holy Hatred: Religious Conflicts of the ‘90’s*, James A. Haught observes that “a great irony of the 1990s is that religion— supposedly a source of kindness and human concern— has taken the lead as the foremost contributing factor to hatred, war, and terrorism” (Awake, August 8, 2001:7) On this line of thought, the culture of Africa is not left out. In his submission, Chirac says:

We blend Africa for four and a half centuries. We looted their raw materials, then we told lies

that the Africans are good for nothing. In the name of religion, we destroyed their culture. And after being made rich at their expense, we now steal their brains through miseducation and propaganda to prevent them from enacting Black retribution against us

(www.theblackpeoplematrix.com)

From history, lots of evil and inhumanity have been perpetrated through religion and the intellectuality of high profiled men of religion. The fore fathers of the church through series of Councils, Synods, Policies, Edicts, etc have purposely called on secular powers to “exterminate the Jews” (Kisch, 1949:203.) Crusades propagated by the 1st ever Christian Roman Empire, Anti-Semitism rooted in the words, beliefs/teachings of some high ranked religious intellectuals for that matter, the Spanish Inquisitions made by Pope Sixtus IV in 1477 and nurtured by Dominican monks like- Miguel de Morillo, Juan de San Martin, et al, the Milan Edict of 313 A.D which aimed at favouring Christianity to the destruction of Judaism and synagogues, and the Holocaust operated and manned by Hitler but rooted and intrinsically supported in the church’s Policies, Edicts, beliefs and teachings, are all derivatives or offshoots and in alignment with the intellectuality of the Fathers of the Church (Hagee, 2007:17-26,125-35) “Anti-Semitism is a synonym for hatred. Christianity is a synonym for love. (Therefore) show me an anti-Semitic Christian, and I’ll show you a spiritually dead Christian whose hatred for other human beings has strangled his faith.” (17) In its actual sense, “Anti-Semitism has its origin and its complete root structure in Christianity, dating from the early days of the Christian church.” (17) As an irony of humanism, “Anti-Semitism in Christianity continued with the writings of the early-church

fathers, a poisonous stream of venom from the mouths of the supposed spiritual leaders.” (20) For instance, John Chrysostom labeled the Jews “Christ killers” (20). Talking of the Jews, Justin Martyr says; “The Scriptures are not yours, but ours” (130) and the Lyon Bishop (Irenaeus) declared that the “Jews are disinherited from the grace of God” (130), and in his treatise, “Against the Jews”, Tertullian proclaimed that the Jews are now forsaken by God for the Christians. (130) For Hilary of Poitiers, the “Jews are a perverse people accursed by God forever.” (132) For Bishop of Cappadocia (Gregory of Nyssa) “The Jews are a brood of vipers, haters of goodness.” (132) The Christian significant figure (St. Jerome) described the Jews as “serpents, wearing the image of Judas, their Psalms and prayers are the braying of donkeys.” (132) We must not forget that the Alexandrian Bishop and Patriarch- Cyril “expelled the Jews and gave their property to a Christian mob.” (134) As an effect, in “Easter, the Christian clergy would enflame the passions of the faithful until the saints would race out of the church with clubs, run to the Jewish quarter, and beat the Jews to death for what they did to Jesus on the cross. It became an annual custom at Easter to drag a Jew into the church and slap him on the face before the altar.” (20) As fierce as it could be, sometime:

This ceremony was sometimes carried out with excessive vigor; on one occasion, recounts a monkish chronicler... a distinguished nobleman who was taking the part of chief celebrant ‘knocked out the eyes and the brains of the perfidious one (disbelieving Jew), who fell dead on the spot’... his brethren from the synagogue took the body out of the church and buried him (Flannery, 1985:51)

At this juncture, “following the anti-Semitic teachings of the early church fathers, the Roman church, in an attempt to take control of Jerusalem, declared it was the will of God”. No wonder then why Hitler says: “I am only continuing the work of the Catholic Church” (Runes, 1968:114) by killing fellow humans after all, they are Christ’s killers and sub-humans. Mission now accomplished, he exclaimed: “I am now, as before, a Catholic and will always remain so” (Toland, 1978:326) In concordance to the Church’s teaching that the Jews are the Christ’s killers, and the enactment of the “Final Solution” to annihilate these killers (Jews), after bombing Pearl Harbor in December 1941, Hitler ordered that the “killings (of the Jews) should be done as humanely as possible” for it goes in line

with “God’s injunction to cleanse the world of vermin” being convinced from “the Catholic teaching that the Jews was the killer of God” (Toland, vol 2, 803). The killing “therefore, could be carried out without a twinge of conscience since he was merely acting as the avenging hand of God”. To ensure collaboration with the church to gratefully achieve this heinous aim, Hitler made a treaty with the church which surfaced in the policy of the church and the Nazi where the “non-human and soulless Jews” were given their position. (Scherer, 1901:39-49) In line with this, we must not forget the Nuremberg Trials interview of a German General regarding the massacre of at least six million Jews by the Germans, and he replied: “I am of the opinion that when for years, for decades, the doctrine is preached that Jews are not even human, such an outcome is inevitable” (Hay, 1981:3) Talking about Luther, Inge writes: “The worst evil genius of Germany is not Hitler, or Bismarck or Frederick the Great, but Martin Luther” whose 95 Thesis nailed to the Cathedral Door and his “Concerning the Jews and their Lies” served and motivated greatly, the eradication of the Jews (166) Buttressing more on Luther, Encyclopedia Judaica, vol. 3, records this:

Let me give you my honest advice... their synagogues... should be set on fire, and whatever does not burn up should be covered or spread over with dirt so that no one may ever be able to see a cinder or stone of it. And this ought to be done for the honor of God and of Christianity in order that God may see that we are Christians... their homes should be broken down and destroyed... they should be deprived of their prayer books and Talmuds in which such idolatry, lies, cursing and blasphemy are taught... their rabbis must be forbidden under the threat of death to teach any more... passport and travelling privileges should be absolutely forbidden the Jews. Let them stay at home... they ought to be stopped from usury... let the young and strong Jews and Jewesses be given the flail,... ax,... hoe,... spade,... distaff, and spindle, and let them earn their bread by the sweat of their noses as is enjoined upon Adam’s children. We ought to drive the lazy bones out of our system. If however, we are afraid that they might harm us personally, or our wives, children, servants,

cattle, etc., then let us apply the same cleverness (expulsion) as the other nations, such as France, Spain, Bohemia, etc., and settle with them for that which they have extorted from us, and after having it divided up fairly let us drive them out of the country for all time. To sum up, dear princes and nobles who have Jews in your domains, if this advice of mine does not suit you, then find a better one so that you and we may all be free from this insufferable devilish burden- the Jews (1978:103)

On a critical note, did Jesus in the bible refer to the Gentiles when he talked of 'dogs' and the 'unclean creature' saga led down from heaven in the sheet? In bewilderment, we may be justified to hold that "Christianity is strange; it bids man to recognize that he is vile and even abominable." However, on a reconciliatory note after much suppression, excommunication and oppression of the church to visionary thinkers of the old, in 2009, Catholic church through the then Vatican Secretary of State Tarcisio Bertone called Galileo— one of the most persecuted— a Man of Faith; and Pope St. John Paul II also apologized to the world on behalf of the church for the direct and indirect sins of the fore fathers as documented by Luigi Accatoli. Actions of the fore fathers of the church were completely inhuman and aimed at denying humanity intellectuality (worst sin) by hiding the truths from the world especially as they contradicted the doctrines of the church then.

From Islamic side as a religion, disregard of the fact that the Father (Ishmael) was not Abraham's legitimate son, and was naturally violent, Mohammed, the Islamic last messenger from Allah, encouraged violence. He motivated and advised the followers that any who refuses to relinquish his faith should be killed for he has "been ordered by Allah to fight with people till they testify there is no god but Allah, and Muhammad is his messenger" (Authority of Ibn 'Abbas.) In its enactment, it is written in the holy Quran/Surah (9:5) thus: "Fight and slay the Pagans (non Muslims-the infidel) wherever you find them, and seize them, beleaguer them, and lie in wait for them in every stratagem (of war)." Again, it was recorded thus:

The punishment of those who wage war against Allah and His Messenger, and strive with might

and main for mischief through the land is: execution, or crucifixion, of the cutting off of hands and feet from opposite sides, or exile from the land: that is their disgrace in

this world, and a heavy punishment is theirs in the Hereafter (Surah, 5:33)

As an offshoot of Islam, the Wahhabism "preach a rigid, intolerant version of Islam that breeds radicalism. The pulpits of these mosques are filled with Wahhabi preachers spouting violence against America and all infidels (Christians and Jews)" (Hagee, 65.) Experts have predicted that Muslims who are enlightened with such violent nature of Islamism without academic mediation, are doom- icons and that generally "15 to 20 percent of Muslims are radical enough to strap a bomb on their bodies in order to kill Christians and Jews, that means there is an Islamic force of approximately 300 million radicals who are willing to die killing you (the infidel- the enemy). We cannot be ignorant of this fact or the recent history that foreshadowed it" (Hagee, 67) just as it is the Nigerian case with the Boko Haram insurgence. "Islam not only condones violence, it commands it" and this answers why the *jihad* must be upheld by the Muslims. Even in conception, Allah, in religion and teaching contrasts Jesus Christ and Jehovah and the Christian and Jewish teachings (Braswell, 44-8; Duck, 2006:152-3)

Today, the irony of intellectuality and humanism in church and the religious leaders is seen in its core nakedness and with no mindfulness to conscience. No religious leader today seem to be humane as it is clear how they exploit the members knowingly and shamelessly let alone speaking for them. Their luxurious life style (even in their acclaimed ecstasy and simplicity and oath of poverty), clear partiality especially when it concerns the rich and the church and another party explain entirely our point here. All in the name of religion, they use humans as means to their own selfish ends. They have practically shown their loss of sense of traditional value in their daily lives. What they now do is 'listen to my words and dare not emulate my behaviour.' They end up preaching to the members but practically not to themselves. On 7th May, 2017 (Catholic Fathering Sunday) during the service, the Pastors ended up preaching and castigating "Papa and Mama" and their parental failure to their families, as they appear to forget that good shepherds lay down their lives for their sheep. The responsibilities of these parents revolve only around their families or extended ones, but they forget that their own responsibilities which they never carry out as Pastors or Reverends are for the whole members of their parishes and stations. Who should condemn who? These are intellectuals whose humanity *ought* to be extra ordinary, but unfortunately and

ironically, what we see in them are *clear cunning, exploitative and parasitic humanism, oppression, exhortation, sadism, impoverishment, rigidity and strictness* under the cloak of being principled and disciplined, partiality and celebration of academics, certificates and material richness that have replaced their supposed fundamental religious mind, spirituality and humanism. At the end of the Gospel reading, instead of preaching what the Biblical passage is teaching, we are rather told of how necessary it is that we religiously keep feeding them (the men of God) and how unavoidably crucial it is, giving ‘fat’ tithes and unblemished offerings without even considering the state of economy which they themselves could clearly see and to finalize the whole preaching, Malachi 3:6-12 must be quoted to remind us that “the wheat and the oil WILL NEVER FINISH in as much as we use them to feed them (the God’s prophets/servants). On Sundays and other religious gatherings, what we end up doing is 2nd collections for Pastors’ car maintenance or changing their “gospel” van by buying the trending fine ones and other obligations, all these, together with our different family responsibilities. They now celebrate intellectual aggrandizement and pride instead of humility and humanity lubricated with obedience, accommodating, consideration, compassion, impartiality, state of being icons of development, morality, enlightenment, spiritual or religious ideals or role models, motivation, et, after all, it is written and taught: “We are a chosen nation, priests in royal position, those whom God himself chose by Himself.” “The endemic problem of man’s inhumanity to man, violent crimes, economic fluctuations, political instability, social unrest, spiritual warfare and so on really make life increasingly difficult which has a resultant effect of unhappiness, feelings of frustration, insecurity, mistrust, etc” (Egbekpalu, 2009:2)

Be that as it may, there are yet some theorists whose thought have encouraged humanism in its practical sense. The 20th century world renowned thinker, Albert Einstein- the brain-child behind atomic bomb invention, Albert Schweitzer, Richard Leakey, having seen the destruction hidden in bomb-invention warned that man should be positive enough in their humanism by minimizing the extent of technological invention so that the existential posterity may not end in doubt (Eneh, 2000:56, 63) Pope Paul VI (1967:34), has earlier warned that:

It is not sufficient to promote technology to render the world a more humane place in which to live. The mistakes of their predecessors should warn those on

the road to development, of dangers to be avoided in this field. Tomorrow’s technocracy can beget evils no less redoubtable than those due to liberalism of yesterday. Economics and technology have no meaning except from man for whom they should serve. And man is only truly man as far as, he is master of his own acts and judge of their worth, he is author of his own advancement

Buddha: This Indian Prince who forsook his supposed throne for “wisdom and truth”, in his *A Refusal to Accept Anger*, maintains that replacement of evil, wickedness, hatred and assault with love, humility and kindness should be upheld by people.

Moralists: The moralists under which we can find the Greek genius, Socrates, opined that Virtue instead of Vice should be sought via education, for there to be no more evil; the Chinese Lao Tzu of 6th century opined that war armaments are intrinsically evil and that the people of Tao (peace) naturally hate them; Mo-Tzu who is also called Mo-ti of China and founder of Mohism opined that the sincere and ground purity of heart is more valuable than ceremonies, rituals and religious activities for the heart may be impure, yet, out of cunning, still participate actively in all these activities. The 3rd century moralist- Mencius of China who taught ‘anti-war’ has asserted that “the more sharp weapons the people have, the more troubled the state will be.” Jesus Christ of Nazareth has earlier posited that love, humility and humane approaches to the hater/evil are the main weapons against evil, violence and wickedness.

Quakers: They believe in the conversion of evil and war to love and peace instead of using force to ensure peace, because this kind of peace stays for a while let alone eternal. The Dutch monk, moralist and humanist, Desiderius Erasmus, in the letter to a Bergis (Antony), in 1513, titled “Complaint of Peace and Antipolemus”, lamented the menace of war, and advised that men should avoid war but seek peace for there is no true joy in the victor who has just been victorious through blood spilling.

David Low Dodge: This New York Presbyterian and merchant in his work, *War Inconsistent with the Religion of Christ*, opined that there is no justification to war. He, together with the English Quakers- William Allen and William Ilyod Garrison

were against war and thus upheld the New England and Non-Resistance Society in America.

Non-violencists: Here are thinkers who think that the best way to manage war/conflict is non-violence. GANDHI- the Indian lawyer is globally referred to as the father of “Non-Violence Approach” to violence/conflict/war for it can bring about a lasting peace. He practiced it in their independence struggle just as he also preached same to the South Africans even in the midst of Apartheid/Racial Policy and to the Jews even in the midst of Nazism. For him, non-violence supersedes all alternatives. VICTOR HUGO- in his address to the “Congress de la Pax”, Paris 1851, preached mediating method in settling conflicts and quarrels, but not war as a resolving means to war. ADIN BALLOU- This associate of Garrison, in his work, *Christian Non-Resistance*, upheld that love should be independent of moral (or religious baseless) for true Christian should, out of love, resist all forms of evil and violence. EMERIC CRUCE: In his *Holy Resolve*, he addressed rulers to be peaceful for peaceful men are, to him, more honourable than warriors hence rulers should be honourable and not dishonourable (war-admirers.) CIVIL DISOBEDIENCISTS: Under this heading, we see people who followed the way of civil disobedience as the alternative means to approach war after all attempts. They opined that when war/evil persists from the authority, the citizens should, out of no other option, embark on ‘civil’ disobedience as a way to demonstrate their frustration or dislike to the happenings perpetrated by the authority in the society. Here are thinkers like Henry David Thoreau who once said, “rather than money, fame, power, give me truth”, Nelson Rolihlahla Mandela- the 1st South African black President, the people’s president and freedom fighter against Apartheid, man of peace and self-sufficiency, Martin Luther King Jnr in his “Pilgrimage to Non-Violence” preached peace and refused to pay American tax which was meant to be used in war against Mexico even though he was the then president and who, through the influence of the Congress of Racial Equity, “led the non-violence Negro bus boycott in Montgomery”- U.S.A, Nnamdi Kanu of Igbo- Nigeria, Danilo Duta, the Russian Leo Tolstoy (Lyof Tolstoy) whose non-violence was articulated in his *The Kingdom of God is Within You*, Odumegwu Ojukwu Chukwuemeka who once justified his civil disobedience in his famous assertion *Because I am Involved*, etc. All these thinkers attacked the government through civil disobedience having experienced persisted dehumanization.

PACIFISM: At its extension, we must commend the peace write ups and advocacy of thinkers like Emile-Auguste Chartier, fondly called Alain- a French teacher and 1st World War soldier and his bosom student- Simon Weil, the author of *The Iliad*; the woman pacifist- Vera Britain whose pacifism was expressed in her epistle, “Humiliation with Honour”; Dorothy Day who published the *Catholic Worker* together with Peter Maurin and many others. They have, in their writings, made it clear that disputes should be settled amicably and that war is always wrong as it leads man to nowhere than doom and existential extinction hence peace, should be sought for.

Conclusions and recommendations

From the foregoing, it is clear that there are two senses of humanism- human intelligible power which is innate but only waiting for a mid-wife to deliver, and on the other hand, the facticity of the humanity of man (as a human being, not an animal, a tree, etc) who deserves dignity, respect, worth, etc. However, it has become a misfortune that what should be of positive impact has now become the sole source of negativity. It has ironically turned to make life miserable and unveil its meaninglessness, worthlessness, un-interestingness, shortness and absurdity. Man is now living in an imperfect and irony-reigning world where betrayal, war and violence and other forms of crimes all as products of the humanism of man have taken the upper hand. Thus, we must advise and make it known that “there ends your right, here begins your duty.” Therefore, men, “lay down your arms, live in peace. On that day, you will be conscious of a common thought, common interest and a common destiny... You will acknowledge that you are sons of the same blood and the same race... On that day, your name will no longer be war but civilization” (Eneh, 2001:118) Our humanism and its practicality have put men into quagmire and doom. Professional violence, inhumanity, frauds, crimes, war, lies, life-threatening inventions and activities of today are, the products of humanism (human intellectuality) in application. It has perpetrated evil and suicidal to humanity. After experiencing the difficulty and hardship that proceeded from socio-economic and political affairs of the people, the Egyptian and indeed 1st world socio-political thinker- Ipuwer of 2500^{BC}, recommended racial suicide as a means of overcoming these life-threatening conditions, and a great number of people succumbed to his advice to get out of socio-eco-political quagmire challenging them (Eneh, 1999:70.) Again, it was recorded of Hegesias of 4th century ^{BC}, an Egyptian philosopher of the Cyrenaic school who would finish giving

lectures at Alexandria “and many people who attended his lectures went afterwards to commit suicide” and it took the intervention of authority to put it to an end (Omogbe, 193, Eneh, 1999:64.) These are indeed the effects of the articulated ideas of man. But it was this suicide that Camus (1975:11) explains thus:

There is but one truly serious philosophical problem, and that is suicide. Judging whether life is or is not worth living amounts to answering the fundamental question of philosophy. All the rest- whether or not the world has three dimensions, whether the mind has nine or twelve categories- come afterwards. Whether the earth or the sun revolves around the other, is a matter of profound indifference. To tell the truth, it is a futile question. On the other hand, I see many people die because they judge that life is not worth living

However, the concluding fact remains that man has, out of the exercise of his humanism, been a source of inhumanity unto himself hence the need to revitalize the whole understanding of humanism and its applications.

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